

**ESTIMATION AND EVALUATION OF LAWSONE IN DIFFERENT HENNA SAMPLES
BY USING VARIOUS ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUES**

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ABSTRACT

Lawsonia inermis, often known as henna, is a natural dye plant that is widely used for cosmetic and medicinal purposes. Its main active component, lawsone (2-hydroxy-1,4-naphoquinone), is what gives henna its characteristic reddish-brown colour and therapeutic properties. In order to determine and assess the amount of Lawsone in both natural and commercial henna samples, the current study used UV-visible spectroscopy, HPLC, atomic absorption spectroscopy, and infrared spectroscopy. Cold maceration and sonication were used to create methanolic extracts for efficient Lawsone recovery. UV-visible spectroscopy was utilized to get λ max and initial quantification. Additionally, an HPLC method was created in compliance with ICH guidelines. The use of Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy was used to assess sample safety and heavy metal detection. The developed analytical techniques were shown to be suitable for henna and were straightforward, accurate, precise, and reliable.

KEYWORDS: Lawsone, Henna, UV-Visible Spectroscopy, IR, HPLC, Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy.**INTRODUCTION**

Determining the quality, purity, and authenticity of various henna samples requires the quantification and assessment of Lawsone. The primary bioactive pigment in henna, lawsone, may be precisely identified and measured using a variety of analytical methods. Reliable data on the chemical makeup, functional groups, and concentration of Lawsone can be obtained using techniques like UV-visible spectroscopy, HPLC, and infrared (IR) spectroscopy. These analytical techniques enhance quality control in both commercial and research applications and aid in the standardization of henna products.

Analytical methods of Modern spectroscopic and chromatographic methods

UV-VISIBLE SPECTROSCOPY: UV-visible spectroscopy is based on the idea that molecules absorb ultraviolet or visible light, which causes electrons to shift from lower to higher energy levels. According to Beer-

Lambert's law, the amount of light absorbed is directly proportional to the substance's concentration.

HPLC: HPLC is that various components in a mixture separate because they interact differently with the stationary phase and the mobile phase. As a result, each compound moves through the column at a different speed and elutes at a different time

INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY: Infrared spectroscopy is that molecules absorb infrared light, which causes vibrational changes like stretching and bending. Only vibrations involving a change in dipole moment result in an IR absorption signal.

ATOMIC ABSORPTION SPECTROSCOPY: AAS operates on the basis that light of a certain wavelength is absorbed by free atoms in their ground state. When a sample is atomized in a flame or furnace, the amount of light absorbed by these atoms is exactly proportional to the concentration of the element present.

DRUG PROFILE

- **Scientific name:** Lawsonia inermis
- **Family:** Lythraceae
- **Genus:** Lawsonia
- **Kingdom:** Plantae
- **Order:** Myrtales

MATERIALS AND METHODS**Study Area**

The entire study was carried out in Sri Venkateshwara College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana in 2025.

CHEMICALS USED

The chemicals used in this study include standard Lawsonone from Sigma Aldrich with 96.5% purity, methanol for HPLC from Merck Life Science and ethanol also supplied by Merck Life Science. Hydrochloric acid was obtained from SD Fine Chem Limited, while HPLC-grade water was sourced from Avantor. Additionally, acetonitrile for HPLC was procured from SD Fine Chem Limited.

INSTRUMENTS USED: The laboratory is equipped with a UV/VIS Spectrophotometer from Lab India, an HPLC system from Shimadzu and Analytical balance manufactured by Sartorius. Additionally, Borosil beakers and conical flasks are used for sample handling, along with pipettes and test tubes for precise measurement and transfer of liquids.

METHODS**MORPHOLOGICAL ANALYSIS**

Different types of Henna samples were collected and morphological characteristics were examined such as plant type, leaves, flowers, leaf type, shape, leaf surface, leaf texture, colour, taste and odour.

PHYTOCHEMICAL ANALYSIS

1. **ALKALOIDS:** The Wagner's test involved dissolving a plant extract in Wagner's reagent, which is iodine in potassium iodide. Additionally, the colour look suggests that the Henna extract contains alkaloids.
2. **AMINO ACIDS:** NINHYDRIN TEST: After dissolving plant extract in 0.25% Ninhydrin reagent and boiling it for a short while, the colour that forms shows that amino acids are present.
3. **PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS:** FERRIC CHLORIDE TEST: 3-4 drops of ferric chloric solution were added to plant extract and the colour

that formed show the presence of phenolic chemicals.

4. **REDUCING SUGARS:** BENEDICTS TEST: 3-4 drops of Benedict's reagent were applied to a plant extract, which was then gently heated. The emergence of colour indicated the presence of reducing sugars.
5. **FLAVONOIDS:** LEAD ACETATE TEST: After adding a few drops of lead acetate to plant extract, the colour changes to show the presence of flavonoids.

QUALITATIVE ANALYSIS OF LAWSONE THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY**Preparation of Standard & Sample solution**

Standard solution preparation involved accurately weighing one gram of standard Lawsonone in a 10-millilitre volumetric flask and then adding 10 millilitres of ethanol to the flask.

Sample solution preparation involved transferring 10 mL of the extracted sample solution into a 10 mL volumetric flask.

Procedure: The TLC analysis was carried out by spotting the standard (plot A) and three samples solutions (plot B, C and D) on to the prepared TLC plate using capillary tubes. The plate was then placed in a beaker containing the mobile phase, prepared with ethanol and acetonitrile and sealed with a Petric plate. Once the solvent front reached about 70% of the plate's height, the TLC plate was removed and allowed to air dry. After drying, the plate was observed under a UV chamber at 283 nm to compare the spots with the standard and confirm the presence of Lawsonone.

METHOD DEVELOPMENT OF LAWSONE BY UV SPECTROSCOPY**Preparation of Standard solution**

In a 10 mL volumetric flask, one gram of standard Lawsonone was dissolved in methanol. After 20 minutes of sonication, the solution was let to cool ambient temperature. Methanol was used to dilute one millilitre of this solution to 10 mL.

Preparation of Sample solution

A 10 mL volumetric flask was filled with one gram of each henna sample, which was then filtered through Whatman paper after being extracted with methanol using cold maceration, occasional shaking, and 15 minutes of sonication. For additional examination, 1 mL of the extract was diluted to 10 mL with methanol after the filtrate had cooled to room temperature.

MULTIVARITE CALIBRATION OF LAWSONE BY UV SPECTROSCOPY**Preparation of sample solution**

In a 10 mL volumetric flask, one gram of each sample was dissolved in methanol. For twenty minutes, the mixtures were sonicated. They were filtered through

Whatman filter paper once they had cooled. Methanol was used to dilute one milliliter of each filtrate to ten millilitres. Methanol was used to dilute one milliliter of each of the test and reference solutions. Next, each solution's absorbance was measured.

VALIDATION PARAMETERS

LINEARITY

Consider the standard to be the blank. Now, make 10 µg/mL of mixture from the sample solution. A number of wavelengths around the drugs λ max (450 nm) are then used to measure absorbance. Accordingly, 444, 446, 448, 450, 452, 454 and 456 nm. The absorbance values of each solution were noted and shown. At various wavelengths, the residual plots and calibration graphs were displayed.

ACCURACY

The test solution receives known additions of Standard Lawsone at 75%, 100% and 125% respectively. 10 mL of the standard solution was pipetted into three separate volumetric flasks from the produced stock solutions of the standard and sample. Then, 0.1, 0.6 and 1.1 mL of the sample solution were added to the volumetric flasks and the volume was increased to 10 mL with methanol. The recovery percentages were computed. Recovery study findings are noted.

PRECISION

Precision is a repeatability process. It is done by taking 30 µg/mL concentration. Precision is performed as intraday and inter-day precision, where one concentration is analysed for 5 times and mean is calculated to find standard deviation and %RSD at different selected wavelengths.

LOD AND LOQ DETECTION

The lowest level of analyte found in the sample is known as the LOD. The lowest quantity of analyte in the sample, as established by accuracy and precision, is known as the limit of quantification (LOQ).

Where,

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 * \sigma/m$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 * \sigma/m$$

ASSAY

The amount of Lawsone in the sample was assessed by measuring the extracted samples absorbance at 450 nm.

Residual plots

Analyte (X) absorbance is measured at seven different wavelengths ($\lambda = 444, 446, 448, 450, 452, 454$ and 456

nm). The following equation can be expressed for each of the chosen wavelengths.

$$C_x = \frac{A_T - K_T}{a=b=c=d=e=f=g}$$

METHOD DEVELOPMENT OF LAWSONE BY RP-HPLC

Procedure

Accurately weight and transfer 1 gram of standard and sample Lawsone into a 10 mL clean dry volumetric flask separately. To this add methanol as diluent and sonicate to dissolve it completely and made-up volume to the mark with the same solvent. This makes the concentration of 0.1mg/ml solution. Measure the regions to determine the amount of lawsone present after injecting 10 µL of the reference sample into the chromatographic apparatus.

DETERMINATION OF LAWSONE BY INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY

Procedure

One millilitre of the extract was diluted with methanol, and then a tiny drop was put on a NaCl plate. To spread the sample into a thin, even layer, the second plate was carefully placed on top. For additional examination, the produced plates were then stored in the sample holder.

DETERMINATION OF LAWSONE BY ATOMIC ABSORPTION SPECTROSCOPY

Preparation of standard & Sample solution

- Lawsone stock standard and sample solutions were prepared.
- Diluted in increments of 0.5, 1, 2, 5 and 10 parts per million.
- Distilled water to dilute the solution to volume after filtering it.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Morphological Evaluation

Characteristics	Observations
Leaf	Simple leaf
Shape of the leaf	Ovate to elliptic
Leaf surface	Smooth and glabrous
Leaf texture	Thin, papery
Colour	Fresh leaves- Bright green
	Dried leaves- Brownish
Taste	Slightly bitter
Odour	Mildly aromatic when crushed

PHYTO-CHEMICAL ANALYSIS

S.NO	Test parameters	Observations
1	Alkaloids (Wagners Test)	Brown Precipitate Was Observed
2	Amino acids (Ninhydrin Test)	Blue Colour Was Observed
3	Phenolic compounds (Ferric Chloride Test)	Bluish Black Colour Was Observed
4	Reducing sugars (Benedicts Test)	Orange Red Precipitate Was Observed
5	Flavonoids (Lead Acetate Test)	Yellow Colour Was Observed

Phyto-chemical analysis of standard

Phyto-chemical analysis of sample

THIN LAYER CHROMATOGRAPHY OF LAWSONE

TLC Profiling of Standard

TLC Profiling of different samples

METHOD DEVELOPMENT OF LAWSONE BY UV-VISIBLE SPECTROSCOPY

The wavelenghts of Lawsone was found at 450 nm by comparing it with standard Lawsone and the samples.

UV – Spectrum of standard Lawsone

UV – Spectra of Sample Lawsone

Linearity Data

1. Linearity data of Lawsone observed at 450 nm.

Conc (µg/mL)	Absorbance (nm)
	450
10	0.402
20	0.611
30	0.816
40	0.986
50	1.171

ACCURACY DATA

CONCENTRATION LEVELS	AMOUNT RECOVERED	STD DEVIATION	% RSD
75%	280.7	0.40	0.5
100%	247.6	0.4	0.5
125%	219.91	0.31	0.4

PRECISION DATA**2. Precision data of Lawsone observed at 450 nm.**

S.NO	INTRADAY	INTERDAY
1	0.816	0.816
2	0.816	0.816
3	0.815	0.816
4	0.816	0.815
5	0.816	0.816
Average	0.8158	0.8158
STD deviation	0.0004472	0.000447214
% RSD	0.05	0.05

LOD AND LOQ DETECTION**Limit of detection (LOD) $\mu\text{g/mL}$**

$Y=3.3*0.0223/0.1063$	Y VALUE (Abs)	σ (slope)	m (Intercept)	LOD
LOD= 3.3* σ /m	0.816	0.0223	0.1063	0.692

Limit of Quantification (LOQ) $\mu\text{g/mL}$

$Y=10*0.0223/0.1063$	Y VALUE (Abs)	σ (slope)	m (Intercept)	LOQ
LOQ=10* σ /m	0.816	0.0223	0.1063	2.098

ASSAY

	ASSAY PARAMETERS (n=3)		AMOUNT OF LAWSONE FOUND
Observation- 1	Standard Abs	2.231	
	Sample Abs	1.823	81.757
Observation-2	Standard Abs	2.231	
	Sample Abs	1.823	81.712
Observation- 3	Standard Abs	2.231	
	Sample Abs	1.831	81.757
	Mean		245.23
	Average		81.74
	STD deviation		0.03
	% RSD		0.1

**VALIDATION PARAMETERS
ACCURACY**

WAVELENGTH	CONCENTRATION LEVELS	AMOUNT RECOVERED	STD DEVIATION	% RSD
444	75	252.3	0.40	0.2
	100	222.6	0.4	0.2
	125	198.19	0.16	0.1
446	75	259.2	0.40	0.2
	100	228.7	0.4	0.2
	125	203.04	0.31	0.2
448	75	253.1	0.20	0.2
	100	222.9	0.2	0.2
	125	198.10	0.16	0.1
450	75	280.7	0.40	0.5
	100	247.6	0.4	0.5
	125	219.91	0.31	0.4
452	75	265.9	0.20	0.1
	100	234.1	0.2	0.1
	125	207.61	0.16	0.1
454	75	275.5	0.20	0.1
	100	242.9	0.2	0.1
	125	215.9	0.16	0.1
456	75	275.6	0.20	0.1
	100	243.2	0.2	0.1
	125	216.14	0.16	0.1

PRECISION
ABSORBANCE VALUES FOR INTRADAY PRECISION

Conc (µg/mL)	ABSORBANCE (nm)						
	444	446	448	450	452	454	456
10	0.736	0.754	0.735	0.816	0.772	0.801	0.802
20	0.736	0.754	0.735	0.816	0.772	0.801	0.801
30	0.734	0.756	0.735	0.815	0.771	0.802	0.802
40	0.736	0.754	0.736	0.816	0.772	0.801	0.802
50	0.736	0.754	0.735	0.816	0.772	0.801	0.802
Average	0.7356	0.7544	0.7352	0.8158	0.7718	0.8012	0.8018
STD	0.0008944	0.0008944	0.0004472	0.0004472	0.0004472	0.0004472	0.0004472
% RSD	0.12	0.12	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.06

ABSORBANCE VALUES FOR INTERDAY PRECISION

Conc (µg/mL)	ABSORBANCE (nm)						
	444	446	448	450	452	454	456
10	0.736	0.754	0.735	0.816	0.771	0.801	0.802
20	0.734	0.754	0.736	0.816	0.772	0.802	0.802
30	0.736	0.754	0.735	0.816	0.772	0.801	0.802
40	0.736	0.756	0.735	0.815	0.772	0.801	0.801
50	0.736	0.754	0.735	0.816	0.772	0.801	0.802
Average	0.7356	0.7544	0.7352	0.8158	0.7718	0.8012	0.8018
STD	0.000894427	0.000894427	0.000447214	0.000447214	0.000447214	0.000447214	0.000447214
% RSD	0.12	0.12	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.06

LOD AND LOQ DETECTION

$$LOD = 3.3 * \frac{\sigma}{m} \quad LOQ = 10 * \frac{\sigma}{m}$$

LOD AND LOQ DATA

WAVELENGTH (nm)	σ (Slope)	m (Intercept)	LOD Values	LOQ Values
444	0.0199	0.1121	0.350	0.022
446	0.0202	0.1120	0.595	1.803
448	0.0164	0.2412	0.224	0.679
450	0.0223	0.1063	0.692	2.098
452	0.0212	0.1138	0.615	1.863
454	0.0209	0.1267	0.544	1.650
456	0.0217	0.1167	0.061	0.186

LINEARITY

Residual Plots

METHOD DEVELOPMENT OF LAWSONE BY RP-HPLC

Optimized method

Stationary phase- Inertsil RP- C18
 Eluent Composition – MP A -Methanol: MP B- HPLC water (60:40)

Spruge rate- 1.0 mL/min
 Quantification – 282nm
 Runtime – 15 min
 Inject volume- 20 µL

Standard chromatogram of Lawsonsone

Sample chromatogram of Lawsonsone

DETERMINATION OF LAWSONE BY INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY

Functional group	Absorption Range (cm ⁻¹)	Values Observed (cm ⁻¹)
O-H	3000 – 3700	3446
C=O	1650 – 1750	1637
C-O	1000 – 1350	1047
C=C	1600 - 1700	1396

DETERMINATION OF LAWSONE BY ATOMIC ABSORPTION SPECTROSCOPY (AAS)

Elements	Limits (ppm)	Values Observed (ppm)
Nickel (Ni)	± 1	0.0244
Copper (Cu)	± 20	0.0964
Lead (Pb)	± 10	0.2113
Cadmium (Cd)	± 0.3	0.0139

CONCLUSION

Using a variety of analytical methods, including UV-visible spectroscopy, IR spectroscopy, HPLC, and AAS, the quantification and evaluation of Lawsone in diverse henna samples revealed significant variations in Lawsone content between natural and commercial samples. The identity and purity of Lawsone were supported by the IR spectrum analysis, which verified the existence of distinctive functional groups. While AAS guaranteed the identification of any heavy metal impurities, UV-visible and HPLC techniques offered precise quantification. All things considered, the combined analytical technique worked well for evaluating the safety, authenticity, and quality of henna products.

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